

MARKET OFFER LEVEL - FINDINGS MATRIX

Market Practices	Composite Activities	Designable Elements	Underlying Single Activities	Consequences	Illustrative Quotes from In-depth Interviews (Sayings)	Excerpts from Unobtrusive Observation and Document Analysis (Doings)		
Exchange Practices	Creating value (AMIT, ZOTT, 2012)	Activities Value	Providing a simple and secure experience	Helps to overcome the feeling of insecurity	<p>"[...] opening an account at Firm B is the same as opening an account at a bank, dude. Same thing, same thing. We will ask for the usual data. We will ask for a photo, we will ask for a selfie. We will do facial recognition. We will do a background check, including police, financial, civil." (P8)</p> <p>"I am a house regulated by the CVM (Movable Values Commission). I have other funds. My goal was: to make a simple, efficient, and fully compliant vehicle with everything that has status-quo, Federal Revenue, CVM, Central Bank, everything, everything." (P15)</p> <p>"We know institutional investors, and this is the background that we see, big investors, they will not come if they do not have a structure for them, so it is 100% safe for them to operate." (P13)</p> <p>"I thought we were already in the movement of providing a lot of transparency, but transparency assumes that the person believes what you are saying, but they brought this proposal. They do not even have to believe us because who will be speaking will be the one's others, this computer network that is doing the operations and is under permanent public scrutiny. This governance is totally public, and then who will speak for us is this computer network." (P6)</p> <p>"So it helps to communicate to the firm, but it is not enough because transparency is just one point, the other is business, which is gone, what is the gain, is transparency with society. What does that reduce in cost, for example, tracking operations, means a lot." (P5)</p> <p>"[...] our paper, it promises poverty reduction and some commitments to sustainable objectives and it brings this dynamic of us to be able to generate social impact for minorities and consequently to improve the local economy, to make things happen." (P17)</p> <p>"The main value proposition was to give liquidity to the asset. To provide convenience." (P7)</p> <p>"So I made an investment fund to try to find out who will be the champions within each category. Sensitive to the price, I enter and leave, so it is the long-only that applies 80% in the top ten leading cryptos and 20% I can invest in other minor cryptocurrencies, or even ICOs. All within the normative instruction of CVM 11/2018." (P15)</p> <p>"The most significant legacy that I would leave if I left the company today is to have brought two thousand families to internationalize their assets and to have protected these families from a devaluation of more than 60 percent within the period from when we started until now. So, just the fact that I provided for these families to protect their assets in more than half of this period, for me, this is already a great legacy." (P11)</p> <p>"I think the biggest difference in what we are doing is bringing this democratization, allowing anyone to have access to this market. It is to pulverize access to investment instead of concentrating income in the hands of a few people." (P11)</p> <p>"I think we are in this with this chance in order to really popularize high-quality access to crypto and consequently contribute to making crypto mainstream on a large scale, as an asset class and fostering technology." (P14)</p> <p>"Look, our mission is to be, as I said, to be a bridge... From the traditional financial market and this new world." (P13)</p>	<p>Firm D has an exclusive section on its website to clarify security, regulation, and governance issues. For example, they highlight that the Movable Values Commission properly regulates crypto-funds and why it is secure to invest with them (content extracted from Firm D website).</p> <p>Firm F has an exclusive page on its website clarifying how transparency is guaranteed for the investors interested in supporting social impactful projects. They contextualize that the investment trail is applied to all stages of the project under development that was supported, being the efficiency and reliability enabled by the tokens implemented through blockchain (content extracted from Firm F website).</p> <p>Both Firm D and Firm E have been recognized by external actors as the ones responsible for the most profitable funds in Brazil, including when compared to multi-market funds (content extracted from news media website).</p> <p>Firm C has pioneered the use of a franchise model in the Brazilian crypto-market. In a specific Instagram post, they mention how important has been this strategy of expanding their reach in Brazil (content extracted from Firm C Instagram).</p>		
			Concretizing transparency	Enables other adjacent and valuable benefits to the society	Working towards return on investment	Clarifies the benefits when compared to traditional financial markets	<p>Both Firm D and Firm E have been recognized by external actors as the ones responsible for the most profitable funds in Brazil, including when compared to multi-market funds (content extracted from news media website).</p>	<p>Both Firm D and Firm E have been recognized by external actors as the ones responsible for the most profitable funds in Brazil, including when compared to multi-market funds (content extracted from news media website).</p>
			Democratizing access to new opportunities	Allows to enlarge the target market	Democratizing access to new opportunities	Allows to enlarge the target market	<p>Firm C has pioneered the use of a franchise model in the Brazilian crypto-market. In a specific Instagram post, they mention how important has been this strategy of expanding their reach in Brazil (content extracted from Firm C Instagram).</p>	<p>Firm C has pioneered the use of a franchise model in the Brazilian crypto-market. In a specific Instagram post, they mention how important has been this strategy of expanding their reach in Brazil (content extracted from Firm C Instagram).</p>

Market Practices	Composite Activities	Designable Elements	Underlying Single Activities	Consequences	Illustrative Quotes from In-depth Interviews (Sayings)	Excerpts from Unobtrusive Observation and Document Analysis (Doings)
Exchange Practices	Delivering value (TEECE, 2010)	Relationships Infrastructure Matching Method	Comprehending the customer segments	Helps to understand the different personas that could be addressed	<p>"We have as primary beneficiaries in this ecosystem, minorities, black people, indigenous people, rural women, artisans, riverside people, affected by dams, settled and resettled, family farming people. It is a very present focus in our business model," (P17)</p> <p>"[...] the client, he has a capital. He has an emergency reserve, and he has a capital that he allocated for venture capital investment. From that amount he invested in venture capital, he takes a part to put in crypto. From that part he puts in crypto, he takes out a part to be able to lease. So the percentage of the investor's aptitude for investing in crypto lease is tiny." (P11)</p> <p>"[...] more classic is that you cut retail investors, high-income investors, and institutional investors." (P14)</p> <p>"So your money does not go to anything else, and for me, over time, a market rise for these people who are willing to pay for this service. I am willing to invest, as long as I have the irrefutable guarantee that my money is going to the right place." (P1)</p> <p>"[...] we went to a level, we created a level of governance, compliance, gigantic security... Thus, higher than what we would do in any other situation because we knew we would charge ourselves for it, for being crypto." (P13)</p> <p>"I think the difference was not that of crypto with a stock fund; from an operational point of view, it is complete. The operational efficiency that a crypto fund has is orders of magnitude above one of stocks. So, as an underlying asset it is very more efficient from an operational point of view, strictly speaking, liquidation, this translates to a much more efficient product. It is impressive... for someone who is from the traditional market, it is impressive to see the productivity gain that exists." (P16)</p> <p>"A cell phone! It is the only thing, right, that you need to be able to acquire. To use it, you have your cell phone, and you can already use it, download the application there, whether you are a physical person or a juridical person, you can do it transactions, charges, transfers, all via the application." (P12)</p> <p>"Our value is embedded in the product, in the application itself, that it is very cohesive, very simple to use. In the functionalities of the application, so the fact that you are using bitcoin, real, and very soon, other cryptocurrencies there too. So it is all there in the hub it is a total one stop shop. It is a beautiful and simple to use application, it is a one stop shop service" (P6)</p> <p>"So no matter how much people want your product, if they cannot easily access it, nobody will want it. So our obsessive focus on working with platforms, preparing our products for platforms that have a very high level of demand look at each of these products." (P14)</p> <p>"So we work with it a lot, we have a very strong inbound marketing. Man, every week there is a new article on our blog, talking about a subject, the articles are always produced thinking about a persona and thinking about a specific keyword to be able to rank on Google, and we write, develop, create a funnel there." (P8)</p> <p>"We have a funnel strategy. I never hid it. So, our most aggressive products were a funnel strategy to create communities." (P11)</p> <p>"So the way to advertise is this, it is to bring people who already have the public's trust, to show what our firm is, and consequently, we will reach people as well." (P12)</p> <p>"[...] But still, it is a niche, it does not have an authority within the market. It is not seen, it is already 10 years in the market, it is not seen as a finance company, it is seen as a finance yet. So it does not acquire authority, it can not break the bubble, and it still continues in the wild west." (P8)</p> <p>"Cryptocurrencies are a prohibited subject on Google. On Google and Facebook." (P6)</p> <p>"What surprised us is how centralized the fund distribution market is still. So the fund could have a much larger size if the distribution market were more homogeneous, which is one, I think it should be an issue horizontal for all projects. The difficulty is always the distribution." (P16)</p>	<p>Firm D and Firm E have launched investment funds covering different investment strategies and fees which helps to approach different customer segments (content extracted by Firm D and Firm E websites)</p> <p>Firm D has conducted in its YouTube channel a live discussing with an international partner the entry of institutional investors in the crypto-market. They also exposed this action the Instagram profile as an relevant initiative that mirrors the attention of Firm D to expose for their customers a secure and regulated view of the market (content extracted from YouTube channel and Instagram profile of Firm D).</p>
			Easing the delivery of value	Facilitates the customer experience	Opens up the market to large capital incomes	

Market Practices	Composite Activities	Designable Elements	Underlying Single Activities	Consequences	Illustrative Quotes from In-depth Interviews (Sayings)	Excerpts from Unobtrusive Observation and Document Analysis (Doings)
Exchange Practices	Capturing value (CHAMBERS; PATROCINIO, 2012)	Transactions Sales Item Pricing	Adopting fees to exchange value	Demonstrates an usual pricing strategy adopted by the market	<p>"Today this part of revenue today involves a lot like the bank. So let us say it, over the fees, right? So handling fees, they are generating profit." (P12)</p> <p>"We start from our value proposition of bringing simple products and bringing products with a low-cost structure. We have passive products then, but we collect an administration fee, which is our primary source of income for our funds." (P14)</p> <p>"Now, in terms of bitcoin and cryptoassets, I see a lot of opportunities. This is where we focus on our pricing. So, today we gain through a kind of marketplace, a spread, when the customer exchanges bitcoin for reais. I can have one efficiency in price. I can arbitrate that price a little bit and get a fee on it. Our main recipe is this, whether in the purchase or in the sale. Selling is more, but also buying." (P7)</p> <p>"In the first months of the project, the metric we used was an Return on Image metric, because that happens in several innovation projects." (P1)</p> <p>"At Firm B, we have our referral program, an affiliate program. You open your Firm B account, you get a referral code, if you call your friend, you, 'low friend, open your Firm B account with your code', automatically you earn five Brazilian reais, for referring someone and you still earn a small commission on every bitcoin purchase and sale that this guy does during one year. It worked very well! This expanded our customer base." (P8)</p> <p>"We have a great responsibility to bring this crowdfunding with us. We are there with 800 people who believed in the project so that we will be together. Through them, we will use them as ambassadors of the project to show my brand around. So it will have a lot focused things on this audience." (P7)</p> <p>"Our main economic issue was more or less the same, making sure that the transaction cost would not make the business unfeasible." (P3)</p> <p>"Now, as I was going to say, what are the challenges in this business of being pureblood with cryptoassets? It is precisely the dynamics of economic transformation because, like this, it is as if we had to, we use this jargon a lot, we use it every month, every fortnight, we have to sell a ferrari. Imagine what it is like to sell a ferrari every fortnight, right?" (P17)</p> <p>"So, I think this pricing part... I see much difficulty in the digital banking part, which is what I said we offer. I offer bill payment, deposit in payment slip, I get almost nothing from it, practically zero. But I need to have this lot of things to meet the persona of the practical." (P7)</p>	<p>In Firm F's whitepaper, there is an exclusive section to elucidate the adoption of fees to operationalize their business model and how these charges may be differentiated for financing and loans (content extracted from Firm F whitepaper).</p> <p>Firm B has pioneered the adoption of equity-crowdfunding in the Brazilian crypto-market. This strategy enabled the company to acquire a considerable quantity of financial resources allocated for investment in technology, infrastructure, and expansion of new services (extracted from a news media website).</p>
			Experimenting different revenue models	Enlight a desire of addressing different ways to exchange value	Recognizes specific cost incomes that has to be considered	Firm B has elaborated an entire page on its website to expose their customers to their services' fees and operational limits (extracted from Firm B's website).